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Paper Title: “A never-ending crisis: the deterioration of health services in Honduras following constitutional changes implemented after the 2009 coup.”

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Short Abstract

Changes to the Honduran national health system evince oft unexamined dimensions of neoliberal policy. I focus on changes following the 2009 coup that limited the obligation of the Honduran government towards citizens by qualifying “deservingness” based on the inevitability of poverty and suffering.

Abstract

I address the sustained/ongoing crisis within the Honduran national health system (NHS) that intensified over the last decade, following a coup in 2009 that led to a constitutional crisis. I argue that the deterioration of the Honduran NHS over the last 15 years should also be related to changes in laws and policies that outlined the overall intent behind the existence of the NHS. Specifically, following the coup in July of 2009, the subsequent democratically elected right-wing government enacted constitutional changes in 2010 that sought to redefine concepts such as “health,” “universal health,” “citizenship,” and the “human,” as well as a reinterpretation of the overall capacity (and obligation) of the Honduran government to intervene on behalf of poor populations to safeguard their health. These changes sought to spur the participation of public-private partnerships and reduce the role of the Honduran Ministry of Health in the direct provision of services and administration of public monies. Although the changes to the NHS have so far been incomplete, these changes appear to have had an impact on the overall quality of service delivery as evinced through some individuals’ experiences when accessing public health services. This has affected how individuals understand both their right to health and their standing as citizens and serves as evidence of how economic speculation is accompanied by dehumanization (Bear 2020). To construct my argument, I rely on a review of the constitutional and legal changes over the last 15 years and in-depth interviews with poor individuals.

Introduction

In this presentation, I juxtapose one participant's experiences within the Honduran national health system with constitutional changes 8 years before that re-defined governmental responsibility in several domains, including health, and that crafted a new understanding of responsible citizenship. These changes in 2010, sought to open the public branch of the national health system to more intensive private investment through public-private partnerships. I call this participant Ana. I met Ana in April of 2018 and I continued to meet with her on a weekly basis for 32 weeks to discuss her and her families health-disease experiences, through what Veena Das (2015) calls morbidity surveys. I continued interacting with Ana and her family on a friendly basis from 2019-2022 and in 2023 I returned to conduct an additional 6 weeks of interviews.

Throughout the time that I have known her, Ana and her family have made frequent use of the national health system, and because they are poor, rely primarily on the public branch of the health system. For Ana, her experience accessing health services served as an opportunity to indirectly evaluate how she was valued within the Honduran social fabric. Ana expressed this in varied terms, sometimes relating to rights and permissions, such as poor people "don't have a right to get sick" or "getting sick is not within poor people's means." With time, Ana more clearly expressed her discontent within the register of what I understand as implicitly acknowledged dehumanization by, for example, sharing "here poor people really have to eat their own shit." For Ana, this was a generalized experience. Simply, "When a poor person gets sick, services are terrible everywhere."

Through Ana's experiences, I consider that it is possible to demonstrate that speculative health reform processes in Honduras depended on an institutional capacity to codify categories of individuals that are not deserving of attention, care or investment, and that this is then later reflected in poor individuals health-disease experiences. In the process, I hope to

illuminate what seems to me to be a limit in the application of health-related deservingness to the honduran context, which is that health-related deservingness does not yet contemplate how neoliberal speculation gives way to codified legal and discursive maneuvers that then impact conceptions of formal rights. In other words, health-related deservingness is more than a moral evaluation and, at least in Honduras, informs formal rights.

Research Context

According to the latest population census from 2013, Honduras had a population of 8,3 million people (INE 2013). 1,05 million of these people lived in the metropolitan área of the central district of Honduras composed by the twin cities of Tegucigalpa and Comayagua. Forty-two per cent of Hondurans had one or more unmet basic needs, 59 percent of households lived under the poverty line, and 36 percent of households lived in extreme poverty. The latest available data from 2016 further indicates that income inequality in Honduras was severe, with 54 per cent of the wealth concentrated in the top quintile, while the lowest quintile only had 4 per cent.

Over the last three decades, the Honduran national health system has been subject to sweeping transformations known as health sector reforms (Carmenate-Milián et al. 2017). The changes implemented during the 1990s were primarily concerned with initiating the slow pseudo-decentralization of public health services (PAHO) 2009). In the 2000s, changes within the health system were more severe owing to the collapse experienced within the national health system after a natural disaster in 1998 (PAHO 2009; SESAL 2009). The latest round of reforms implemented at the beginning of 2010 has taken a somewhat different approach. Instead of making amendments or changes to existing legislation that only partially altered the functioning of the national health system, the government in power made sweeping and constitutionally binding legislation that reformulated the role of government

itself as complementary to private capital investments and stressed citizenship as based on individual empowerment. These latest changes were implemented after the national party, a right-wing party, reached power after a coup against Manuel Zelaya in 2009. From 2009 to 2019, through the Ley de Vision de Pais (La Gaceta 2009), approved in 2010, and the Law for decentralization for Development (La Gaceta 2012), approved in 2012, many of these decentralization and privatization processes were accelerated throughout the country. Particularly, within the Vision de País, the national party established the teleological principles on which subsequent modernization legislation would be based during the next 28 years, that is until 2038, with the ultimate intent to modernize the state by fomenting speculation in the public sector.

Deservingness

Kristen Yarris and Heide Castañeda define deservingness as “the way in which some groups, but not others, are considered worthy of attention, investment or care” (2015: 66). Although they note that deservingness assessments are evaluations emanating from the perspective of a state, they also adopt Sarah Willen and Jennifer Cook’s (2016) argumentation that stresses evaluations of deservingness should be distinguished from conceptions of formal rights. In regards to this, Willen writes that “unlike rights discourses, which presume blindness to individual particularities, deservingness assessments typically are relational” (Willen and Cook 2016: 97). For Willen and Cook, as well as for Yarris and Castañeda, evaluations of deservingness are mainly characterized as evaluations that shed light on subtle and poorly examined moral positions within a given social context (Willen and Cook 2016: 97). Willen and Cook concentrate on examining health-related deservingness and argues that health-related deservingness is based on presuppositions, prejudices and other precepts that are generally regarded as “common sense” (2016: 96). For Willen and Cook, these processes of evaluation

serve as evidence that evaluations of deservingness are emotional responses that highlight personal convictions and beliefs in regard to any given situation. For this reason, Willen maintains that evaluations of deservingness should be understood as originating from a “vernacular moral register” (2016: 96), and affirms that ideas of deservingness “are vernacular expressions of value as opposed to juridical notions of rights. As such, deservingness...is reckoned in ways that are relational, conditional, context-dependent, syncretic, affect-laden, and mutable” (113-114). This for me turns the problem of resource distribution and access to public goods, in this case the provision of public health services, from a formal legal bureaucratic concern to one related to the impact of the exercise of public opinion in curtailing rights in practice, since rights discourse assumes that we all have access to the same rights and procedural justice assumes rights will be justly distributed

However, following from philosopher Sylvia Wynter (1984), it is possible to argue that diverse types of texts should be viewed, and studied, as veiled codifications of dominant values, which through their textualization become naturalized as self-evident values. As a recapitulation of the notion of rights in existence and in practice within a country, we should also, then, understand legal and constitutional codes as a recapitulation of vernacular moral evaluations. In circular fashion, these vernacular moral evaluations find justification within existing legal and constitutional codes. In this way, we could presume the spread of presuppositions, prejudices, and common sense within conceptions of formal rights, that are not acknowledged as presuppositions, prejudices, and common sense since they are elaborated from a dominant perspective which considers these universal and transcendental values.

Here it is useful to think about the work carried out by Laura Bear and Nayinika Mathur (2015) public goods, where they argue that the increased participation of neoliberal speculators in public governance has led to a shift in how we generally understand both the role of bureaucracy as a tool of governance and our understanding of the social contract that

bureaucracies are meant to uphold in favor of a social body. For Bear and Mathur, the original role of bureaucracy was to preserve a social contract based on the distribution of public goods, which they understand as any resource that is generally regarded as providing a positive benefit to society as a whole. With the entrenchment of neoliberal precepts in contemporary bureaucracies, based on the ideal of the free-market and a rational consumer ethos, bureaucratic arrangements increasingly privilege language and practices based on efficacy, efficiency, profits, and cost reduction that seeks to re-orient bureaucracies towards creating environments friendly to private capital investments. And although there is a pretense that these coordinations are value neutral and rational, these new arrangements are in reality aspiring to an idea of the imagined future, and in this way bureaucracies are introduced into the realm of speculation. Again, taking from Bear, we should remember that to speculate it is first necessary to identify groups of individuals that can be expropriated in the present to both generate immediate value and a promise of future value through sustained expropriation. Thus, speculation redefines the social contract not only to privilege capital, but to privilege the creation of capital through a re-evaluation of who deserves access to a public good.

Addressing the conditionality of deservingness and formal rights

To stay within the allotted time, here I will address the concept of conditionality proposed by Willen and Cook (2016), and will try to relate how the vernacular moral register of health-related deservingness already found its way into Honduran legal codes and social experience through the speculation on public goods proposed by the Vision de Pais. Conditionality is evaluating an individual's health-related deservingness by drawing from a subject's pre-existing characteristics. That is, belonging, a priori, to some previously identified group.

One of the 17 "Guiding Principles for Development" of the Vision declares that "the state will promote public-private partnerships for service provision...this is way it will guarantee

efficient and transparente management, as well as modernization (La Gaceta 2010: 22).” The Vision also specifies that the fundamental role of any central government should be complementary and secondary to the participation of private enterprise, exemplified by “subsidiarity” (La Gaceta 2010: 20). Under this model, government interventions in public affairs are reduced to state charity providing a bare minimum necessary for life, as opposed to guaranteeing the preservation and protection of generally agreed upon rights. The Vision reaffirms this position by noting that “social and economic development” is “results from individuals’ efforts to achieve their own well-being” (La Gaceta 2010: 20). This to me suggests the implicit understanding, as a country steeped in extreme poverty, that the average honduran citizen has proved unable to secure their own well-being, leading to a social and moral failure by failing to uphold the desired values of development and modernity foregrounded in the Vision. Through this discourse, the average honduran citizen is located outside of an imagined social evolutionary line, presumably composed of the individuals that do demonstrate said values.

When I met Ana, she was 52 years old and lived with her 32-year-old niece, Katia, her own two teenage children, and with her niece’s three pre-teen children. When we met, Ana had been unemployed for 2 months, although she had had steady employment for the last 4 years prior. When we started talking, Ana was seeking intermitent treatment at several local publics clinic and a public hospital for her high-blood pressure, gastrointestinal issues related to her colon, and a hernia that she developed while providing physical at-home-care for both her brother and a cousin. Ana’s experiences with the health system included both finding solutions and alternatives to her own health-disease needs, but also navigating medical providers as a primary healthcare advocate for individuals in her immediate and extended family.

Ana's primary daily concerns were financial and immediate, relating to her ability to provide daily sustenance for her household. She regularly noted that this gave her a great deal of anxiety, which led to spikes in her blood pressure and increased pain in her colon. Both of these conditions made it difficult to search for employment, but it was primarily the hernia she developed that made it painful and difficult to perform the physically demanding labor she was sometimes contracted to perform. She continues to have all three health conditions.

Although Ana was clearly worried about the progression of her respective ailments, she had difficulty in finding a solution that would allow her to attend to her medical needs without faltering in another arena. She said, "I came back crying...i'm sick, penniless, and I'll have to wait and see how much I have to spend on that treatment...It's horrible...what I am afraid of is leaving it alone, because this will get worse...It will get worse." Ana described a particular exchange with a physician at a local public clinic where she tried to be frank about her situation, hoping this would make the physician understand her particular difficulties in maintaining certain treatment regimens, like reduced mobility. The physician commented: "Look, the only place you should be going to is the bathroom. That's where you need to go." To which Ana replied: "Doctor, I need to run errands, I need to get money to feed my kids...And she says to me: well, go beg. Beg. She tells me...Beg...Right here in the health center." Meanwhile, Ana was engaged in intermittent paid work for some family members and a new church, but always came back to the consideration that work itself is what made it difficult to take care of her health conditions. Once when we were talking about how she felt, physically, performing her current jobs, she simply said to me "time keeps passing and passing and passing. That's what makes me so desperate...because the days that I will be able to get work are getting farther and farther away."

Tentative Conclusion

Introducing speculation into the Honduran constitution, led to framing access to health as a matter of rational investment in private services and the need to eliminate expenditures on public goods. To justify the elimination of public goods necessary to make way for speculation, health-related deservingness was made part of formal conceptions of rights in Honduras by identifying populations not deserving of investment and care. Ultimately, the ethical thrust of existing legislation frees the Honduran government from the responsibility of guaranteeing the well-being of the population, since this possibility is already framed as an impossibility because the poor are a racialized and suspect population.

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